

Effect of Mental Imagery Program on Serving Skills of Volleyball Players

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Abstract

Under the theory of mental imagery, it may be assumed that visualizing skills such as serving, spikes, blocks or defensive play can strengthen the neural pathways which are related to motor skills involved in performing these skills. The objective of the study was to assess the effect of 02 month mental imagery program on the serving skills of male volleyball players. It was hypothesized that two months of a supervised mental imagery program will significantly improve the serving skills of male volleyball players. To conduct the study 50 intercollegiate male volleyball players were selected from tournaments conducted in the State of Chhattisgarh. The average age was 21.12 years. The sample selection was based on the purposive sampling method. Out of these 25 male volleyball players were assigned to the experimental group and 25 male volleyball players were assigned to the control group. The serving skills of selected male volleyball players were assessed through the subjective rating of judges. The five point rating was used by three judges to evaluate service skill such as poor, fair, good, very good and excellent. A two month long mental imagery intervention protocol was chalked out by the investigator after consulting an eminent sports psychologist. Based on suggestions a mental imagery script was prepared which is based on PETTLEP model propounded by Holmes and Collins (2001). The mental imagery program related to service includes 10-minute sessions for five days a week. The result reveals a statistically non-significant impact of 02 months of mental imagery on the serving skills of male volleyball players. It was concluded that the effect of two month mental imagery program did not improve the serving skills of male volleyball players during the short duration of this study. Hence further research is required to assess the longer duration of mental imagery intervention on the serving skill of male volleyball players with modified methodologies.

Keywords: Mental imagery program, serving skills, volleyball

Introduction:

Sportspersons put in hours of physical training to excel in sports but there is more in success in sports. Hence apart from physical, physiological and cognitive

training, mental imagery under sports psychology has gained popularity to enhance the performance of the sportspersons. The term mental imagery /rehearsal is defined as the imagination of a motor task or environment regarding a sports skill or motor movements. Richardson (1967a) defined mental imagery as rehearsing in the mind without actual physical movements. Sackett (1934) also labelled mental imagery as a symbolic rehearsal of motor movements. Murphy (1994) reported that 90% of athletes use mental imagery training for the Olympics or major events even during the tournament and coaches also believe that mental imagery can enhance performance. The psycho-neuromuscular theory of Carpenter (1894) opined that when a person imagines some physical and motor movements it is ever so slightly similar to movements done in the actual physical environment. This framework is also supported by Suinn (1980). The work based on bio-informational theory made assumptions of mental imagery based on long-term memory of our brain. There are approaches for mental imagery intervention and PETTLEP is one of the popular approaches. It consists of seven components namely (P) Physical component, (E) Environmental component, (T) Task component, (T) Timing component, (L) Learning component, (E) Emotional component and (P) Perspective respectively. This model is based on Lagrangian theory (Carroll et al., 1982).

According to Materns (1987), just as athletes differ in physical abilities, they also vary in their capacity for mental imagery. Moran (1993) added that pre-post research often raises concerns about results because of these individual differences. They emphasized that mental rehearsal techniques work only when athletes have strong mental imagery skills. If an athlete lacks this ability, instructions during imagery sessions may not be effective. On the other hand, athletes with good imagery skills are more likely to benefit from such techniques.

Another important factor is cerebral lateralization, which suggests that left-handed and right-handed players may use mental imagery differently. Therefore, coaching instructions should consider whether an athlete is left or right-brain dominant. Perry and Morris (1995) highlighted that for a mental imagery program to be successful, three key elements are essential: the quality, vividness, and controllability of mental images. Athletes who excel in these areas are more likely to achieve better outcomes through mental imagery training.

The role of mental imagery in athletic performance enhancement has been documented by many researchers so far its impact on the serving skills of volleyball

players has not been assessed. Under the theory of mental imagery, it may be assumed that visualizing skills such as serving, spikes, blocks or defensive play can strengthen the neural pathways which are related to motor skills involved in performing these skills. Mental imagery may also be helpful in volleyball regarding game awareness, anticipation and executing motor skills under match pressure. To scientifically understand the effect of a mental imagery program on the serving skills of volleyball players, this study was conducted.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Arjeria and Sanjeev Kumar (2015) evaluated the 8 weeks mental imagery program on penalty shoot accuracy of handball players. The mental imagery program requires players to imagine taking a penalty in a tied match situation successfully. It was found that after the mental imagery program, the penalty accuracy of handball players was significantly improved.

Phulkar and Kagzi (2017) in their study used hypnosis as an intervention and found its meaningful efficacy in enhancing the performance of cricket players.

Iftikhar et al. (2018) in an experimental study evaluated the impact of motor imagery intervention on the reaction time of elite sprinters. The duration of two weeks of mental imagery is based on PETTLEP model. It was found that the reactive ability of elite sprinters saw a significant improvement after a mental imagery program of two weeks.

Yadolahzadeh (2020) in their study reported that a mental imagery program was helpful in reducing psychological stress in junior-level swimmers.

Rahman and Islam (2021) determined the effect of a single session of mental imagery on the free throw accuracy of male basketball players. 20 male basketball were divided into experimental and control groups. It was found that the free throw accuracy of male basketball players was significantly increased after a single session of mental imagery.

Sneha Sindhuja and Pooja Varma (2023) evaluated the effect of mental imagery on athletes' perception of their abilities. It was found that after taking part in the mental imagery program, athletes were more confident about their skill sets and the outcome of the competition.

Objective of the Study

To assess the effect of two month mental imagery program on the serving skills of male volleyball players.

Hypothesis

It was hypothesized that two months of a supervised mental imagery program will significantly improve the serving skills of male volleyball players.

Methodology**Sample :**

To conduct the study 50 intercollegiate male volleyball players were selected from tournaments conducted in the State of Chhattisgarh. The average age was 21.12 years. The sample selection was based on the purposive sampling method. Out of these 25 male volleyball players were assigned to the experimental group and 25 male volleyball players were assigned to the control group.

Tools**Serving Skills**

The serving skills of selected male volleyball players was assessed through the subjective rating of judges. The five point rating was used by three judges to evaluate service skill such as poor, fair, good, very good and excellent.

Mental Imagery Program

A two month long mental imagery intervention protocol was chalked out by the investigator after consulting an eminent sports psychologist. Based on suggestions a mental imagery script was prepared which is based on PETTLEP model propounded by Holmes and Collins (2001). The mental imagery program related to service includes 10-minute sessions for five days a week.

Procedure

50 intercollegiate male volleyball players were selected and divided into two equal groups i.e. experimental and control group. The mental imagery program was given to male volleyball players of the experimental group while both groups continued their usual training schedule. The data on service skills was collected twice i.e. pre-test and after two months of the study period (post test) during intra-squad matches. Data was tabulated and statistical analysis was carried out. Results are given in Table 1 and 2 respectively.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1
Comparison of Pre-Post Test Judges Scores on Serving Skills of Male Volleyball Players of Experimental and Control Group

	N	Pre-Test		Post-Test		't'	Sig.
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Experimental Group	25	2.52	0.96	2.72	1.33	0.20	0.67 ^{NS}
Control Group	25	2.24	1.01	2.32	0.94	0.08	0.33 ^{NS}

Not Significant^{NS}

Table 1 reveals that in male volleyball players of the experimental group, the mean score on serving skills was increased slightly during study period i.e. pre-test mean of 2.52 increased to 2.72 in the post test evaluation. The difference in pre-post test scores on serving skills of male volleyball players of the experimental group was statistically non-significant with $t=0.67$, $p>.05$ confirming this finding.

Table 1 reveals that in male volleyball players of the control group, the mean score on serving skills was increased slightly during the study period i.e. pre-test mean of 2.24 increased to 2.32 in the post test evaluation. The difference in pre-post test scores on serving skills of male volleyball players of the control group was statistically non-significant with $t=0.33$, $p>.05$ confirming this finding.

Table 2
Comparison of Gain Scores (Post-Pre) on Serving Skills of Male Volleyball Players Experimental Vs Control Group

Serving Skills	Experimental Group (N=25)		Control Group (N=25)		't'	Sig.
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Gain Score	0.20	1.47	0.08	1.18	0.31	$p>.05$

Table 2 shows that the gain score on serving skills of male volleyball players from the experimental group (Mean gain = 0.20) and control group (Mean gain = 0.08) did not differ significantly. Although the serving skills of male volleyball players receiving 02 months of a mental imagery program increased ever so slightly as compared to the control group the $t=0.31$ did not confirm this finding statistically.

The result reveals a statistically non-significant impact of 02 months of mental imagery on the serving skills of male volleyball players. Results may be described on the following grounds - a. Serving skills requires long-term practice and a two month mental imagery program may not be sufficient to correct the flaws in service quality of male volleyball players, b. mental imagery alone can not improve service quality in volleyball if players lack a sufficient degree of skill set and c. players may be lacking in cognitive abilities and imagery techniques.

Conclusion

It was concluded that the effect of two month mental imagery program did not improve the serving skills of male volleyball players during the short duration of this study. Hence further research is required to assess the longer duration of mental imagery intervention on the serving skill of male volleyball players with modified methodologies.

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